

RECENT TRENDS OF ONLINE BANKING IN RURAL DEVELOPMENT OF INDIA

Neetu Singh
Prof. (Dr.) Richa Singhal

Department of Management studies,
Sunrise university, Alwar-Rajasthan

ABSTRACT

The development and the increasing progress experienced in the Information & Communication Technology coupled with the expansion of the global economy paved the way for the transformation of the Indian banking system's role from traditional trade financing to mobilizing and channeling financial resources more effectively in almost all facets of life. Intense competitive environment, changing business environments, globalization and the advancement of ICT are the important factors that have forced Banking and Financial services to change. Customers are also demanding greater convenience and accessibility as reflected in longer branch opening hours and an increase in the choice of delivery mechanism. Therefore, with the passing of the traditional banking sector to electronic banking, new strategies have become necessary in order to attract new and retain existing customers. Banks are the main stimulus of the economic progress to play a vital role in spearheading the economic development of the nation.

Key-Words: ICT, ATM, RBI, PMJDY, NEFT.

INTRODUCTION

Banking through electronic channels has gained increasing popularity in recent years. This system, popularly known as 'e-banking', provides alternatives for faster delivery of banking services i.e. offering, supplying and delivering banking products and services to a wide range of customers at their office or home through various electronic delivery channels via electronic devices. It is a generic term encompassing internet banking, telephone banking, mobile banking etc. It provides lot of benefits which add value to customers' satisfaction and to reach out

consumers through many routes in terms of better quality of service offerings such as ATMs, telephone, internet and wireless channels which are now available to the consumers to perform their banking transactions in addition to the traditional branch banking and at the same time enables the banks gain more advantage over other competitors.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A review of existing literature reveals the impact, challenges, trends and development made by e-banking in the Indian banking sector.

Aggarwal (2003), in his paper '*E banking for comprehensive E-Democracy: An Indian Discernment*', looked for such avenues and evaluated that e-banking could play significant role in E-democracy for successful online bill payment, online brokerage, online account management and anywhere banking and finally, concluded that e-banking services provide one stop service and informational unit that provides great benefits to banks, customers, employers and government.

Raghavan (2006), opined in his article '*Perception of Indian banks in 2020*', that at present over 85% of the finished payment transactions are electronic and traditional way of doing banking at the branch level has relatively little importance to electronic banking users. Many banks including PSU banks would have online ATMs, phone banking, virtual banking, e-banking, Internet banking, etc. by 2020.

Mohan (2006), in his article titled '*Information Technology on Indian banking*', remarked that Indian banking is at the threshold of a paradigm shift and a significant development has been achieved by banks in offering a variety of new and innovative e-banking services to customers today, which was not thought of before. However, public sector banks have not been able to harness the benefits of computerization.

Uppal and Chawla (2009), in their study titled '*E-Delivery channel-based banking services: An empirical study*', found that the customers of public sector, private sector and foreign banks in Ludhiana district of Punjab are interested in e-banking services, but at the same time are facing

problems like inadequate knowledge, poor network, lack of infrastructure, unsuitable location, misuse of ATM cards and difficulty to open an account.

Banking Sector in India

- Credit off-take has been surging ahead over the past decade, aided by strong economic growth, rising disposable incomes, increasing consumerism & easier access to credit
- As of Q3 FY18, total credit extended surged to US\$ 1,288.1 billion.
- Credit to non-food industries increased by 9.53 per cent reaching US\$ 1,120.42 billion in January 2018 from US\$ 1,022.98 billion during the previous financial year.
- Demand has grown for both corporate & retail loans; particularly the services, real estate, consumer durables & agriculture allied sectors have led the growth in credit.
- The digital payments revolution will trigger massive changes in the way credit is disbursed in India.

Indian Banking Industry Analysis:

The Indian banking system consists of 27 public sector banks, 21 private sector banks, 49 foreign banks, 56 regional rural banks, 1,562 urban cooperative banks and 94,384 rural cooperative banks, in addition to cooperative credit institutions.

As of Q4 FY17-18, total credit extended by commercial banks surged to Rs 86,825,727 million (US\$ 1,347 billion) and deposits grew to Rs 114,792,883 million (US\$ 1,781 billion). Assets of public sector banks stood at US\$ 1,518 billion in FY17.

Indian banks are increasingly focusing on adopting integrated approach to risk management. Banks have already embraced the international banking supervision accord of Basel II, and majority of the banks already meet capital requirements of Basel III, which has a deadline of March 31, 2019.

Reserve Bank of India (RBI) has decided to set up Public Credit Registry (PCR) an extensive database of credit information which is accessible to all stakeholders. The Insolvency and Bankruptcy Code (Amendment) Ordinance, 2017 Bill has been passed and is expected to strengthen the banking sector.

Deposits under Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana (PMJDY) are growing Rs 78,952.09 crore (US\$ 11.78 billion) were deposited and 31.95 million accounts were opened in India[^]. In May 2018, the Government of India provided Rs 6 trillion (US\$ 93.1 billion) loans to 120 million beneficiaries under Mudra scheme. In May 2018, the total number of subscribers were 11 million, under Atal Pension Yojna.

Rising incomes are expected to enhance the need for banking services in rural areas and therefore drive the growth of the sector.

The digital payments revolution will trigger massive changes in the way credit is disbursed in India. Debit cards have radically replaced credit cards as the preferred payment mode in India, after demonetisation. Debit cards garnered a share of 86.79 per cent of the total card spending.

What is Internet Banking?

Internet banking involves consumers using the Internet to access their bank account and to undertake banking transactions. At the basic level, Internet banking can mean the setting up of a Web page by a bank to give information about its product and services. At an advance level, it involves provision of facilities such as accessing accounts, funds transfer, and buying financial products or services online. This is called "transactional" online banking.

There are two ways to offer Internet banking. First, an existing bank with physical offices can establish a web site and offer Internet banking in addition to its traditional delivery channels. Second, a bank may be established as a "branch less, Internet only, or virtual bank" without any physical branch.

Banking services through Internet

(A). Levels of Banking services

Broadly, the levels of banking services offered through INTERNET can be categorized in three types:

(i) The Basic Level Services use the banks' websites which disseminate information on different products and services offered to customers and members of public in general. It may receive and reply to customers' queries through e-mail,

(ii) In the next level are Simple Transactional Websites which allow customers to submit their instructions, applications for different services, queries on their account balances, etc, but do not permit any fund-based transactions on their accounts,

(iii) The third level of Internet banking services are offered by Fully Transactional Websites which allow the customers to operate on their accounts for transfer of funds, payment of different bills, subscribing to other products of the bank and to transact purchase and sale of securities, etc.

Most of the banks providing Internet banking products and services offer, to a large extent, an identical and standard package of banking services and transactional capabilities.

(B). Structure of Banking services

In general, Internet banking products are offered in a two-tiered structure.

* A basic tier of Internet banking products includes customer account inquiry, funds transfer and electronic bill payment.

* A second or premium tier includes basic services plus one or more additional services such as

1) Brokerage. 2) Cash management. 3) Credit applications. 4) Credit and debit cards. 5) Customer correspondence. 6) Demat holdings. 7) Financial advice 8) Foreign exchange trading. 9) Insurance. 10) Online trading. 11) Opening accounts 12) Requests and intimations. 13) Tax services. 14) E-shopping. 15) Standing instructions. 16) Investments. 17) Asset management services etc.

Traditional Banking vs. Internet Banking:

In traditional banking, the customer has to visit the branch of the bank in person to perform the basic banking operations viz., account enquiry, funds transfer, cash withdrawing etc.,

On the other hand, E-banking enables the customers to perform the basic banking transactions by sitting at their homes or at offices through a desktop or laptop round the clock globally through electronic media. This is called any time, any where banking. The customers can access the banks' website for viewing their account details and perform the transactions as per their requirements. Customers can make use of these services with no restricted banking hours, no queues, no tellers and no waiting.

E-banking Transactions:

The following are some of the basic functions in Internet Banking:

- Account Enquiry
- Fund Transfer
- Payment of Electricity, Water and Telephone bills
- Online payment for transactions actually performed through Internet
- Request for issuance of cheque books, demand drafts etc.,
- Statement of accounts
- Access to latest schemes
- Access to rates of interest and other service charges

Models for E-Banking

To implement effectively E-banking and augment the level of technology the following models have been suggested:

(i) Complete Centralized Solution (CCS).

(ii) Cluster Approach.

(iii) High Tech Bank within Bank.

Daniel (1999) defines electronic banking ‘as the delivery of bank’s information and services by banks to customers via different delivery platforms that can be used with different terminal devices such as a personal computer and a mobile phone with browser or desktop software, telephone or digital television’. It includes RTGS, NEFT, ECS, Credit cards/Debit cards and Smart cards, CTS, ATM kiosks and Mobile banking.

Table –1 showing the progress of computerization and automation in Indian banking sector

Stages	Objectives and Technology applied	Developments
Pre-Nationalized Stage Private control of banks (before 1969)	Higher profitability and Manual work	NA
Post-Nationalized Stage Control of Govt. (1969 – 90)	Social Banking and Limited Computerization	1984-88 • Installation of ALPMs. • Banks started using personal computers with hard disk. • MICR cheques were introduced at four metro centers. 1990 • Experimentation of total branch computerization covering all aspects of bank’s transactions at the branch level.
Economic Reforms Stage Entrants of foreign and Social Banking to IT based Banks (1991 – 2000)	Higher profitability, cut throat competition and E-banks	1991 • India joined SWIFT. 1997 • Shared payment network system has been set up. 1999 • A pilot project for smart cards conducted jointly by RBI, IIT (Mumbai) and IDRBT, Hyderabad. 2000 • IT Act, 2000 was passed.
Present Stage Implementation of various committees report (2000 – till date)	New products and Services and Maximum use of IT- Mobile, ATMs	2003 • Special EFT system was introduced. 2004 • RTGS system was introduced. 2005 • 11% of branches of PSBs have been brought under CBS and NEFT system was introduced. 2007 • The payment and settlement system act, 2007 was enacted. 2008 • The operative guidelines on mobile banking transactions were issued. • CTS were implemented in national capital region. 2009 • Cash withdrawal from ATMs of the banks was made free of cost.
Source – Compiled by Author		

Indian Perspective – Presently, country’s banking industry has been consistently working towards the development of technological changes and its usage in the banking operations for the improvement of their efficiency. With the application of new and improved technologies, Indian banks expected to reduce costs, time and give full customer satisfaction. Core banking applications has changed the face of banking by offering value added services. As a result, there is a significant transformation in every sphere of the Indian banks, especially in governance, nature of business, style of functioning, delivery mechanism and also the changes occurred in the financial markets, institutions and products.

Table 2-showing number of banks in India:

Important Indicators	As on 31st March						
	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2013	2016
SBI Group	8	8	8	7	7	6	7
State-owned banks	20	20	20	20	20	20	22
Private sector banks	28	25	23	22	22	21	22
Foreign banks	29	29	28	31	32	34	34
Regional rural banks	133	96	91	86	82	82	82
Non-scheduled commercial banks	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
Scheduled commercial banks	218	179	171	166	165	165	171
<i>Source: Statistical table relating to Banks in India/RBI.(2016-2017)</i>							

It is important to note that presently almost 98% of the branches of public sector banks are fully computerized and within which almost 90% of branches are on CBS platform. Growth rate in case of fully computerized branches and branches under CBS has increased whereas in case of partially computerized branches it has declined.

Table 3- showing the computerization in Public Sector banks (%)

Categories	Year					
	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017
a) Branches under core banking solutions	11	28.9	44.4	67.0	79.4	90.0
b) Branches already fully computerized (other than branches under core banking solution)	60	48.6	41.2	26.6	15.6	7.8
Fully computerized branches (a+b)	71	77.5	85.6	93.7	95.0	97.8
Partially computerized branches	29	22.5	14.4	6.3	5.0	2.2
<i>Source: Statistical table relating to Banks in India/RBI.(2016-17)</i>						

Technological Development of E-banking in India – Up gradation of technology, innovation and modernization are the key factors of having excellence in banking sector. Technological innovation not only enables a broader reach for consumer banking and financial services, but also enhances its capacity for continued and inclusive growth. The different ways on which

internet is trying to revolutionize the delivery of the financial services and products are given below –

1. a) **Automated Teller Machine (ATM)** – It is an electronic machine operated by a customer himself to deposit or to withdraw cash from bank. ATMs reduce the work pressure on bank’s staff and avoid queues in bank premises and help a lot to travellers as they need not have to carry large amount of cash with them as well as can withdraw cash from any city or state, across the country and even from outside the country. The growth of volume of ATMs indicates that customer most prefer ATMs for transactions because they do not want to go to branches for their day to day banking transaction as shown below in Table-IV.

Table 4- showing the growth of bank group-wise ATMs of scheduled commercial banks:

Bank Group	Year (As at end-March)								
	2012 – 2013			2013- 2014			2014 – 2015		
	On-site ATMs	Off-site ATMs	Total No. of ATMs	On-site ATMs	Off-site ATMs	Total No. of ATMs	On-site ATMs	Off-site ATMs	Total No. of ATMs
I. Public sector banks	29,795	19,692	49,487	34,012	24,181	58,193	40,241	29,411	69,652
1.1 Nationalised banks*	15,691	9,145	24,836	18,277	12,773	31,050	20,658	14,701	35,359
1.2 SBI Group	14,104	10,547	24,651	15,735	11,408	27,143	18,708	13,883	32,591
II. Private sector banks	10,648	13,003	23,651	13,249	22,830	36,079	15,236	27,865	43,101
2.1 Old private sector banks	26,411	1,485	4,126	3,342	2,429	5,771	4,054	3,512	7,566
2.2 New private sector banks	8,007	11,518	19,525	9,907	20,401	30,308	11,182	24,353	35,535
III. Foreign banks	286	1,081	1,367	284	1,130	1,414	283	978	1,261

All SCBs (I+II+III)	40,729	33,776	74,505	47,545	48,141	95,686	55,760	58,254	1,14,014
--------------------------------	---------------	---------------	---------------	---------------	---------------	---------------	---------------	---------------	-----------------

Source: Report on Trends and Progress of Banking in India, RBI, Mumbai, (2013, 2014, 2015).

Note: *Include IDBI Bank Ltd. (12-13) *Excluding IDBI Bank Ltd. (13-14), *Excluding IDBI Bank Ltd. (14-15).

b) Debit card and Credit card- It is a card which designate to customer to withdraw own money from the bank in any time that is to say, used for cash withdrawal from ATM, funds transfer, paying bills, accessing detail account information, changing PIN etc.

Credit card is a post paid card and the holder of the card is empowered to spend money wherever and whenever he wants with his credit card within the limits fixed by his bank

Table 5- showing the bank group-wise outstanding number of debit cards and credit cards issued by SCBs

Bank Group	Year (As at end-March)					
	Outstanding No. of Debit Card (in million)			Outstanding No. of Credit Card (in million)		
	2013	2014	2015	2013	2014	2015
I. Public sector bank	170	214.6	260.6	3.08	3.1	3.5
1.1 Nationalised banks*	80	103	118.6	0.78	0.84	0.9
1.2 SBI Group	90	112	136.4	2.3	2.22	2.6
II. Private sector banks	53	60	67.3	9.32	9.7	11.1
2.1 Old private sector banks	12	13.9	15.4	0.04	0.04	0.04
2.2 New private sector banks	41	46	51.9	9.28	9.63	11.1
III. Foreign banks	3.9	3.8	3.3	5.64	4.92	5.0
All SCBs (I+II+III)	228	278.4	331.2	18.04	17.65	19.5

Source: Report on Trends and Progress of Banking in India, RBI, Mumbai, (2013, 2014, 2015). Note: Figures may not add up to the total due to rounding off.
 *Excluding IDBI Bank Ltd. (14-15)

Table V showing Bank Group-wise outstanding number of debit cards and credit cards issued by scheduled commercial banks as at end March 2013, 2014 and 2015. In 2013-14, Public sector banks have highest number of debit cards issued by the industry has increased from 170 million in 2013-2014 to 260.60 million in 2014-2015. Nationalized Banks (118.6 million) and SBI group (136.4 million) have high percent of cards issued as compared to Private sector banks (67.3 million) in 2014-2015. The share of new private sector banks is higher as compared to old private sector banks. Foreign banks have (3.3 millions) in 2014-2015 of debit cards issued. The Table V also shows outstanding number of credit cards issued by scheduled commercial banks as at end March 2015. The number of credit cards issued has increased from 3.08 million in 2012-2013 to 3.5 in 2013-14. In 2014-2015 the total cards issued in case of private sector banks is highest (11.1) in comparison to 2012-2013 (9.32). The share of public sector banks is just 17.07% and that of foreign banks is 31.26%. Foreign banks have (19.5 millions) in 2014-2015 of credit cards issued.

Conclusion:

The study has a number of contributions to both theory and management practice. The outcomes from this study can be used by bank managers to identify the tech-savvy customers and their effects on banking and Indian Economy. The understanding of various adoption factors and barriers will enable them to devise strategies to promote the mobile banking adoption in India. The demographic characteristics identified by this study can be used to devise strategies effectively to promote the adoption to various identified segments. The study provides guidelines to banks and other financial institutions to know the key drivers influencing mobile banking usage intention. For this, the study attempted to find the quality of internet banking services, which is gaining popularity in India. The quality attributes and measuring their satisfaction will help the banks to improve the service quality of internet banking services, which will increase the satisfaction level and continued use of this service. The quality attributes identified from this study can be used to improve the internet banking products of their banks.

References:

1. Capgemini(2014). World Payments Report.
2. (1994) Stanford Federal Credit Union .Online Banking.
3. Nelson P, Richmond W (2007) Internet Banking: Gold Mine or Money Pit? Academy of Banking Studies Journal 6: 1-25.
4. Jasimuddin SM (2000) Saudi Arabian Banks on the Web. Journal of Internet Banking and Commerce
5. Diniz, E (1998) Web Banking in USA. Journal of Internet Banking and Commerce
6. Chang YT (2003) Dynamics of Banking Technology Adoption: An Application to Internet Banking. Warwick Economics Research Papers, University of Warwick, UK.
7. Siaw I, Yu A (2004) An analysis of the impact of the internet on competition in the banking industry, using porter's five forces model. International Journal of Management 21: 514-522.
8. Afuah A (2003) Redefining Firm Boundaries in the Face of the Internet: Are Firms Really Shrinking. Academy of Management Review 23: 34-50.
9. Yibin Mu (2003) E-Banking: Status, Trends, Challenges and Policy Issues. proc. of CBRC Seminar, The Development and Supervision of E-banking, Shanghai.
10. Thulani D, Tofara C, Langton R (2009) Adoption and Use of Internet Banking in Zimbabwe: An Exploratory Study. Journal of Internet Banking and Commerce.
11. Chakravorti S, Kobor E (2002) Why invest in payment innovations? Federal Reserve Bank of Chicago Working Paper.
12. Furst K, Lang W, Nolle D (1998) Technological innovation in banking and payments : industry trends and implications for banks. Office of the Controller of the Currency Quarterly Journal 17: 23-31.
13. Berger AN, DeYoung R (2006) Technological progress and the geographic expansion of commercial banks. Journal of Money Credit and Banking 38: 1483-1513